

Integrating Artificial Intelligence in the Design of Interactive Experience. Synoptic table

Design Phase	Design (Sub)Task	Name and URL of the resource
1. Inspirations	Identification of Existing Resources [1.1]	Semantic Scholar, https://www.semanticscholar.org/
		Consensus, https://consensus.app/
		Scite, https://scite.ai/
		Elicit, https://elicit.com/
	Single Source Analysis [1.2]	ChatPDF, https://www.chatpdf.com/
2. Definitions	Understanding the User [2.1]	Grain, https://grain.com/
		Looppanel, https://www.looppanel.com/
		QoQo, https://qoqo.ai/
		Kraftful, https://www.kraftful.com/
		Notably.AI, https://www.notably.ai/
	Modelling the User [2.2]	QoQo, https://qoqo.ai/
		UserDocAI, https://userdoc.fyi/
3. Design	Definition of the Design Brief [3.1]	GoodBrief, https://goodbrief.io/
		Design Brief Generator, https://aiplanet.com/apps/design-brief-generator
	Definition of Mock-Ups and Wireframes [3.2]	Visiily, https://www.visiily.ai/
		Uizard, https://uizard.io/
		UI-AI, https://ui-ai.com/
		Magician, https://magician.design/
		Galileo AI, https://www.usegalileo.ai
		html-to-design, https://html.to.design/home
4. Prototyping	Natural Language Generation, Translation and Storytelling	ChatGPT, https://chatgpt.com/
		Gemini, https://gemini.google.com/app

		Claude, https://claude.ai/
		Sudowrite, https://sudowrite.com/
		Jasper.AI, https://www.jasper.ai/
		Plotfactory, https://plotfactory.com/
	Image Generation	DALL•E, https://openai.com/dall-e-3
		Midjourney, https://www.midjourney.com/home
		Dreamstudio, https://dreamstudio.ai/
		Getty Images AI Gen., https://www.gettyimages.co.uk/ai/generation/about
		Adobe Firefly, https://www.adobe.com/it/products/firefly.html
	3D Asset Generation	Dreamfusion, https://dreamfusion3d.github.io/
		Point•E, https://openai.com/index/point-e/
		Gaudi, https://machinelearning.apple.com/research/gaudi
		Magic3D, https://research.nvidia.com/labs/dir/magic3d/
		MVDream, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2308.16512
		Meshcapade, https://meshcapade.com/
		Masterpiece, https://www.masterpieceex.com/
		Ponzu, https://www.ponzu.gg/
		Spline, https://spline.design/ai
		3DFY.AI, https://app.3dfy.ai/
Sloyd, https://www.sloyd.ai/		
Gliastar, https://lumalabs.ai/		
Fotor, https://www.fotor.com/features/ai-3d-model-generator/		
Alpha3D, https://www.alpha3d.io/		
Luma AI, https://lumalabs.ai/		

		DeepMotion, https://www.deepmotion.com/animate-3d
		Rokoko Vision, https://www.rokoko.com/products/vision
		Meshy AI, https://www.meshy.ai/blog/create-stunning-cultural-heritage-3d-models-with-generative-ai
		Kutlu et. al 2023, doi: 10.2312/qch.20231160
		Jaramillo-Sipiran 2024, doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2410.10927
		Stoean et al. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.culher.2024.07.008
		Neuralangelo, https://research.nvidia.com/labs/dir/neuralangelo/
	Audio and Audiovisual Content Generation.	Text-to-speech by IBM, https://www.ibm.com/products/text-to-speech
	Text-to-Speech	MurfAI, https://murf.ai/
		Lovo, https://lovo.ai/
		Synthesis, https://synthesys.io/
		Speechify, https://speechify.com/
		Verbatik, https://verbatik.com/
	Audio and Audiovisual Content Generation.	AIVA, https://www.aiva.ai/
	Music	Soundful, https://soundful.com/
		Eccret Music, https://eccretmusic.com/
		Suno AI, https://suno.com/
	Audio and Audiovisual Content Generation.	Sora, https://openai.com/sora
	Video Generation	Runway, https://www.deepbrain.io/
		InvideoAI, https://invideo.io/
		synthesia, https://www.synthesia.io/
	Code Development	Tabnine, https://www.tabnine.com/
		IBM Watson Code Assistant, https://www.ibm.com/products/watsonx-code-assistant

		GitHub Copilot, https://github.com/features/copilot
		Figma Dev. Mode, https://www.figma.com/dev-mode/
5. Testing		User Testing, https://www.usertesting.com/platform/AI
		AppliTools, https://applitools.com/
		Maze, https://maze.co/
		Muse, https://muse.stream/en/
		Synthesized, https://www.synthesized.io/
		Synthetic User, https://www.syntheticusers.com/